

MECHANISM FOR REINTEGRATING CHILDREN IN CONFLICT WITH THE LAW BASED ON CUSTOM: AN ALTERNATIVE MODEL IN THE REFORM OF THE CHILD CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The Child Criminal Justice System (SPPA) in Indonesia emphasizes a paradigm shift from a retributive approach toward restorative justice, but the mechanism for social reintegration of children in conflict with the law remains the weakest point in practice. The lack of social support, societal stigma, and minimal inter-agency collaboration causes many children to fail to function normally after going thru the judicial process. The purpose of this research is to formulate a customary-based reintegration mechanism as an alternative model capable of bridging the gap between national legal norms and local wisdom. This research uses a juridical-empirical method, examining the provisions of the SPPA (Child Criminal Justice System) and analyzing social practices thru customary institutions in resolving child cases. The research results indicate that the formal institutional roles of the Correctional Center, Special Child Development Institutions, families, communities, and local governments have not been optimal due to limited structural and social support. Conversely, customary institutions provide a more comprehensive mechanism, ranging from customary mediation, relationship restoration, community-based social supervision, to moral-economic support that strengthens reintegration. Additionally, customary law has social and constitutional legitimacy that allows its role to be integrated into the SPPA. In conclusion, customary-based reintegration is a relevant, contextual, and potentially alternative model for strengthening restorative justice and social recovery for children within the juvenile justice system.

Keywords: *Child Criminal Justice System, Child Reintegration, Customary Law, Restorative Justice.*